

Plant-inspired Remote Controllable Snap-Fastener for Robotic Micromanipulation

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Abstract— Here, we introduce a plant-inspired controllable micro-snap fastener for the remote release of objects at the microscale. The devices consist of two complementary parts, an “active hooked part” (realized with an array of *Rosa arvensis*-like microspines), and a “passive looped part”. They were microfabricated at high resolution using two-photon lithography directly, or in combination with micro moulding and casting of thermoplastic polycaprolactone with incorporated gold nanoparticles (PCL@Au NPs). The microfabricated PCL@Au NPs-based microspines enable remote, near infrared laser-controlled stiffness variation (hard/soft) using a reversible phase transition of the PCL by plasmonic heating of the Au NPs. Besides, the potentiality of a proof-of-concept untethered remotely controllable device for easily clasping and releasing objects is demonstrated. Our technology shows great potential for micromanipulation tasks in harsh scenarios, such as space environments.

Keywords— plant-inspired machines, micromanipulation, 3D micromanufacturing, microspines, plasmonics, space technology

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of novel plant-inspired intelligent and multifunctional materials has obtained an increasing interest in soft- and micro-robotics [1, 2]. For instance, several devices have been recently fabricated by mimicking climbing plants[3-6], which adopted different anchoring systems to colonize harsh environments (e. g. twining, coiling, adhesive pads, adventitious roots and hook-like structures[7-10]). Here, we report a novel, remotely-controllable micro-snap fastener with micropatterned spines inspired by the climbing plant *Rosa arvensis* ‘Splendens’[4]. Firstly, we designed the artificial microspines (MS) based on the shape of natural spines. Secondly, we microfabricated an array of MS structures using two-photon lithography (DLL) directly or in combination with micro-moulding and casting techniques to obtain MS made of thermoplastic polycaprolactone (PCL) with incorporated gold nanorods (PCL@Au NPs). Thirdly, we proposed a *proof-of-concept* demonstrator for easily clasping and releasing a weight by a light-based remote control using a near infrared NIR laser operating at a wavelength of 808 nm (matching the plasmonic peak of the Au NPs) to locally vary the temperature of the MS by plasmonic heating. Finally, we introduced the prototype of a “hook and loop” micro-snap fastener for robotic micromanipulation.

II. FROM NATURAL TO ARTIFICIAL MICROSPINES

We take inspiration from the natural shape of *Rosa arvensis* ‘Splendens’ prickly-like spines (Fig. 1a), due to their peculiar tip down-ward orientation and their high resistance to mechanical stress[11]. On the basis of the natural geometry extracted from analyzing plant samples (e.g., diameter, length, width and angle, Fig. 1b), a biomimetic 3D model of

rose spines was developed (Fig. 1c). Then, we scaled the size of the biomimetic natural model down (1:16) in order to use our device for micro-scale robotic tasks. The artificial microspines have been fabricated using a combination of DLL, micro-moulding and casting of PCL@Au NPs. The final microfabrication process has shown exceptional results in terms of quality and resolution, particularly evident at the level of the tip (Fig. 1d).

Fig. 1. Bioinspired design and fabrication of *Rosa arvensis* spines. (a) Natural rose prickly-like spines. (b) Morphometric analysis of natural rose spines. (c) 3D biomimetic CAD model obtained in SolidWorks® of the rose spine. (d) SEM image of an individual down-scaled artificial microspine made with PCL@Au NPs. Adapted from [4].

III. REMOTE CONTROLLABLE MICROMANIPULATION

A *proof-of-concept* device with an active array of microspines was developed and tested for its capability to release objects by a controlled stiffness variation (Fig. 2). We recorded the experiment in real time (the optical and schematic views of the tests are reported in Fig. 2a-c and d-f, respectively), which consisted of different steps. At time 0s, a weight (2 grams, applying ~20 mN to a single MS) was interlocked at an individual MS (Fig. 2a, d). Then, a 808 nm laser with a power of 188 mW[4] was used to irradiate the device which immediately heats due to the plasmonic effect to an average temperature of about 40°C after 25 seconds increasing up to 43°C after 50 seconds [4]. This leads to stiffness variation of the PCL but does not prompt irreversible melting [12]. Hence, the MS becomes more flexible and the spine tip starts to slowly bend. After 49 seconds, the tip bending is visible (Fig. 2b, e) and a second later, the soft spine released the weight and the tip turned instantly back (Fig. 2c, f).

Fig. 2. (a-f) Proof-of-concept rose-like device with active microspines to demonstrate controllable release of objects. (a-c) Microscope view (extracted from a video) of a spine, which interlocks a loop with a weight of 2 grams at

the (a) starting time (laser OFF, time: 0s); after (b) 49 and (c) 50 seconds (laser ON, 188 mW). (d) Schematic draw of the controllable release process: (d) at the starting time, the material of spines is stiffer and it can hold a weight of 2 grams; (e) when the laser is turned on, the spine becomes soft and starts to bend, until (f) it releases the object and turns back. Reproduced from [4].

IV. HOOK AND LOOP SNAP-FASTENER FOR ROBOTICS

To create a novel “hook and loop” controllable micro-snap fastener for micromanipulation applications, the active hooked part was associated to a complementary inactive looped part (Fig. 3). The hooked part consists of a patch of 5x5 rose-inspired microspines (Fig. 3a), while the looped part consists of a patch of 5x5 loops array (Fig. 3b). SEM images showed great microfabrication output with high resolution and reproducibility of both hook and loop parts (Fig. 3a, b). These two complementary parts can be easily interlocked (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. Rose-inspired hook and loop micro-snap fastener. (a) Hooked part of the device: Describe software view (upper part) and SEM images of the frontal (middle part) and lateral view (lower part) of rose spines array and of single rose spine. (b) Looped part of the device: Describe software view (upper part) and SEM images of the frontal (middle part) and lateral view (lower part) of loops array and of single loop.

Fig. 4. Lateral microscope view of single spine and loop interlocking.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

We proposed a novel climbing plant-inspired micro-snap fastener and successfully fabricated it at the microscale. Moreover, we demonstrate that a microspine can hold a 2-grams weight which is about 500000 times heavier of its own weight (i. e. individual spine has a weight of 3.7 μg). Thus, we recorded the clasping and releasing of the weight by remote laser-controlled heating of PCL@Au NPs-made microspines, demonstrating the potential of our technology for micromanipulation tasks.

The possibility to create a remotely controllable snap fastener to manipulate and release small size objects has high potential in extreme scenarios, such as remote space environments. These miniature fasteners can be integrated into a robotic arm or in multifunctional plant-like growing robots (i.e., GrowBots, Fig. 5) for collecting and releasing

precious microsamples via precise remote laser irradiation. Achieving a faster actuation response (e.g. < 1s) may be needed for specific applications (e. g. immediate release in space environments). The heating due to the plasmonic effect of the AuNPs is extremely fast (< 1s) but the limiting part is the heat transfer to the PCL and AuNPs. In future works, the particle numbers, their distribution and the laser power may be optimized to increase heating and melting of the PCL and thus to achieve a faster actuation response of the device.

Fig. 5. Towards a new generation of GrowBots embedding *Rosa arvensis*-like microspines.

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